

Paper 7

NETWORK SECURITY: THREAT & MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Security these days is very important issue and required in all the organizations and institutions irrespective of nature. Computer Security is closely associated with Information Technology Security. Network Security is a vast world and it has a close connection with the Database Security, Web Security and Cloud Security. Network Security is required due to various issues viz. vulnerabilities, malware, spyware, ransomware, Trojan, virus, phishing, denial of services, web shells etc. There are different threat management defending systems viz. computer access control, application security, authentication, authorization, firewall, intrusion detection systems, mobile secure gateway etc. Day by day the intelligence system is developing and as a result threat is also increasing. Corporate world, industries are employing different smart devices and there threat management systems is highly required. This is a basic paper on Network Security and talks about the aspects of Network Security with special reference to the threat management. Paper deals the fundamentals affairs of threat management as well.

Keywords: IT Management, Information Assurance, Threat Management, Network Security, IT Security Policies

1. Introduction :

Network Security is an important concept and field within IT Security. The field is responsible for dealing different network related securities viz. technologies that prevent or defend network privacy and security related issues. Initially during the development of the concept of security in respect of computing; there was no as such concept. That time only Computer Security concepts was there but gradually other security related concepts have been emerged and among these Network Security is treated as important and most valuable [1], [5]. Network security is actually the responsible for the authorization of access to data within the network, and normally it has administrated by the network administrator. Network security is deals different types of computer networks including public and private. And most of these are used in everyday jobs. Network Security is applicable and important in different sectors and fields viz. healthcare and medicine, business and commerce, research and development, education and training, government and administration sectors etc. Network Security and Management is the need of

hour [2], [3], [7]. Today, Network Security is concern about different areas viz. Trojan, worms, virus, malware, spyware etc. Similarly, backdoor, denial of services etc are also important name these days.

2. Objective and Agenda

The current paper entitled ‘Network Security: Threat Management’ is theoretical and nature and deals with basics affairs related to the Network Security viz.—

- To learn about the basics of Network Security including its basic characteristics and nature.
- To know about the importance and need of Network Security in different sectors and fields at a glance.
- To learn about the root and threats related to the Network Security in basic sense.
- To know about the basics of Network Security threat management.
- To learn about the challenges and issues in response of Network Security Management.

3. Network Security Threats

Network Security initially started with the authentication by using user name and password. And the one step verification to two step or even three step verification methods can be adopted. Firewall is another name for securing information and contents [4], [8], [10]. Apart from these firewall few other are also important viz. – antivirus etc. The following contents is concentrated on different threats like—

Computer Crime & Network—

This is the crime related to the computer and network itself. Computer crime may be done the individuals or group to the individuals or group. Cyber crime may also called the affecting or harming any computer or whole computer system viz. networks, database, mobile phones, internet systems etc.

Vulnerability & Network —

In Network Security, another important name is vulnerability. It is simply the weakness of the network. Normally the attacker finds the vulnerability to perform unauthorized attack or performs. Initially it was called as security risk. There are certain things that can be fall under the vulnerability viz. security bug, password management flaws, unchecked user input, intrusion detection systems, vulnerability inventory etc [6], [9], [11].

There are different types of vulnerability viz. hardware vulnerability, software vulnerability, network vulnerability etc. However apart from these, vulnerability can be of following viz.—

- Vulnerability related to the Organization (like failure or lacking in planning, audits);

- Vulnerability in respect of Physical sites (may be in inappropriate place, threats of natural disaster etc);
- Vulnerability in respect of Human Resources (may be inadequate or less awareness of vulnerability or security technologies) etc [12], [13], [16].

There are different ways to exploits vulnerability viz.

- An attacker can find out the vulnerability in the systems and based on this, the attacker can install the malware to collect the sensitive data etc.
- An attacker can send any suspicious email for getting any personal information using malware or spyware etc [14], [15], [18].
- There may be invalid validation that exploits vulnerability viz. code injection, cross site scripting, email injection, SQL injection, clickjacking, FTP bounce attack, side channel attack.

Malware & Network —

Malware is a kind of program responsible for damaging computer systems that includes computer, server, network or databases. There are different kinds of Malware viz. computer virus, worms, trojan, adware, scareware etc. Malware has a malicious intent. Initially Malware based attack was started in the government organizations and institutions but gradually it has become common tool for attack to the common people by the network [17], [21], [22].

Malware is also designed for the monitoring user's web browsing history including the spyware related activities. Malware is affected following, normally—

- Software
- Database
- Network etc

USB port can be used to spread malware and thus it is an important way which is used by the attackers. There are different types of malware and these category are increasing. Ransomware is also a kind of malware responsible for financial fraud and extort money from computer users. Ultimately malware is dedicated to infected the systems. It is thus designed to damage to a standalone system/ computer or even a network. Initially malware was created by the hackers, but in recent past Government agencies are also used the same. There are different means for malware management and among these important are—

- Not to use suspicious or strange emails.
- Double checks the systems and contents before its downloading.
- Only reliable advertisement is better to check or click.
- Careful viewing of reliable and trusted websites are very important.

It is worthy to note that; phishing websites, fake apps, and unofficial app stores are these days dangerous for mobile devices (android based) as well. There are different threat management

system developed and among these in Windows 10 ‘Windows Defender Security Center’ important one.

Spyware & Network —

Spyware is a kind of malware. It is mainly dedicated to collect the information and content from the device without acknowledging the users. Even spyware is able to control the whole device (i.e. hidden). It normally uses cookies for the same. Spyware mainly may be classified into following four, mainly—

- Adware
- System Monitor
- Tracking Cookies
- Trojans etc

Spyware is mostly uses pop-ups to collect the data. However, sometimes few Spyware (like Keyloggers) may be used in the organizations to collect the information from the employee. Through spyware, one can collect any type of information of the devices and specially internet habit these days. Some spyware can change the internet systems and settings as well. In Some countries Spyware is allowed in Governmental affairs to deal the task and here another concept is arrived called ‘*Govware*’ and this is mainly common in German countries. A spyware installation is the result of changes in unwanted CPU activity, disk usage, network traffic. Some spyware is even able in removing anti-spyware, anti-virus and few even able in reducing less network security function [12], [19], [20].

There are different anti-spyware, block spyware available in the market and their usages are also rising rapidly due to market need. But it is worthy to note that still many such anti- Spyware are not working to remove all Spyware from the systems especially in Symantec, Microsoft etc. Here re-installation of the OS and data transformation is the only way to solve the problem.

Hence for a secure Network System needful should be provided in respect of Spyware and allied malware.

Virus & Network —

Computer Virus or simply, ‘Virus’ is a kind of malware. It is an important and most popular threat to the Network Systems. Though, apart from the network systems the general computer and electronic devices also affected with the Virus. Though it is a kind of malware but the term Virus is widely known and popular in public space. The main reason for the Virus is to infecting the vulnerable systems use administrative control and to get users personal, sensitive data. Some Virus are also responsible for the replicate the data. There are different ways to get or infected Virus and among these few important are—by email attachment, infected files, executable files etc. There may be different infection vectors viz.—

- Software Bugs

- Poor security practices in Social Media and Engineering places
- Weak Operating Systems etc

There are different kinds of Virus viz. Resident Virus, Non Resident Virus, Resident Virus, Macro Virus, Boot Sector Virus, Email Virus etc. A Virus can infected different computer in a same network if enters and thus System and Network Administrator need to handle the task very carefully. Sometimes, Viruses can be available in the free apps, funny videos, images etc.

Worms & Network —

Worms normally not changes or deletes the contents, it is generally responsible for the replicate the files or objects. It is a kind of Malware, the virus whereas need a host to infect or to operate, but worm doesn't requires any host. A worm once enter into the system it start its operation of replicate the files etc. Many a times, it enters by the network system or internet etc. The worm can be following types viz. –

- Email Worm
- IM Worm
- IRC Worm
- Net Worm
- P2P Worm etc

It is worthy to note that worm normally enters as network packets. Moreover worm can exploit the network configuration error. Hence instead of locally like virus, a worm can infected the computer systems or network worldwide instantly. Hence in Network system, worms are more essential to care off. The following table: 1 shows the worm and virus features in general sense.

Table: 1-Depicted the differences and characteristics of the virus and worms

Characteristics	Virus	Worms
Dependencies	Host File Based	No host file needed, it is standalone
Human affiliation	Human intervention	No Human intervention needed
Infected Facets	The files and infected files can be shared one by one	Normally act by the Network Operation
Core Activity	Normally damages files and systems	It can consume the network bandwidth and replicate files
Working zones	Work via executable files	Work by the vulnerable network
Corrupting systems	Can corrupt/ shutdown the system	Can corrupt/ shutdown the network

Backdoors & Network —

Backdoor in Network is an important concept. Network or system administrator may install a backdoor program for solving a problem. *This is enable* threat to gain command-and-control and moreover move laterally across the targeted *network*. *In otherword, it is* a method that hackers use for the establishment of unauthorized access to a *network* from a remote place. Backdoor may also take the form of a hidden program [8], [14], [19].

Backdoor threat is noticeable when many users in an organizations and used network operating systems. There are different example may be noticeable in backdoors viz—

- Emilla Attack
- Object Code Backdoor
- Asymmetric Backdoors

Hackers can use backdoor to install malware for the purpose of modify code or detect files and gain system or data access.

Denial of Service & Network —

Denial of Service (DoS) is a kind of attack in Information Technology Security. It is a kind of cyber attack in which whole network resources may be unavailable temporarily from the host network. There is a subfield of DoS called, Distributed Denial of Service and Network (DDoS). Another field is—Advanced Persistent DoS. According to the US-CERT following may indicate an Denial of Service (DoS) attack—

- Degradation of the network performance; mainly during the opening files stored in a network.
- Less network strength in when accessing websites and web portals.
- When a particular website is unable to reach.
- The Denial of Service (DoS) may be notified when higher volume of spam email is noticeable.

Phishing & Network —

Phishing is a kind of Cyber Security attack in this kind of cyber offence email play a big role for the attack. In Phishing, attackers normally send the malicious virus by a message or email with the attachment. Normally in phishing attackers are plans to collect users information mainly confidential and financial in nature. It is one of the early cyber attacks which exists in 1990s. It is still most popular and useful. With the Phishing Kit, one can easily do the Phishing; the following diagram (source: CSO-India i.e. <https://www.csoonline.com/article/2117843/>) shows it clearly.

Fig: 1-Anatomy of a Phishing Kit.

There are two types of Phishing, ‘handover sensitive information’ and another is ‘Download malware’. In other words, Phishing can be classified as Spear Phishing Attacks and Whaling Attacks [4], [9], [21].

Eavesdropping & Network —

Eavesdropping is concerned with the network technology and security. It is more clearly associated with the telecommunication systems. Eavesdropping is the technique and procedure that is dedicated to the listing private conversation of communication without consent. This is most illegal practice and treated as worldwide. Eavesdropping is includes the vectors viz. cellular network, email, VoIP, telephone lines etc. It is a kind of unauthorized real-time in the private communication viz. phone call; instant message and even this include the videoconference or fax transmission. With IP-based calls (than that of TDM-based calls), eavesdropping become very easy to perform. Here with the help of protocol analyzer one can pick as well as record the calls and without acknowledging the callers and even they couldn’t here the same. Different software are available of PCs which can convert digitized sound from general CODECs into WAV files.

In other word, Eavesdropping is as an electronic attack and here listening to digital or analog voice communication can be possible with the proper tools. Thus these days, Network

Administrators have to be aware about these due to safety of information privacy. It is worthy to note that, there is an allied concept Network Eavesdropping which is a network layer attack having lack of encryption. Here when a computer send a file of text from one computer to another or one network to another the data privacy become lost. This is important to note that, this is linked to the collection of metadata. These are normally performed by the black hat hackers. However, in recent past Government agencies are also practicing the same, in case of exception requirement.

Advanced Persistent Threat & Network —

Advanced Persistent Threat in short called as APT. It is an important Network related issues and techniques. This is a systematic and robust cyber attack program responsible to collect data and information from an individual computer or group of computer from the same or different network. Advanced Persistent Threat is managed by the group of attackers and that may be hackers or ethical hackers. It is may be undertaken by the government agencies as well. These kind of threat run by the experiences hackers and can run few months and even year/s to reach the goal. As mentioned in the Wikipedia, there are different Advanced Persistent Threat group and among these few important are include—

- American Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Chinese Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Vietnamese Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- North Korean Advanced Persistent Threat Group
- Russian Advanced Persistent Threat Group etc.

It is important to note that traditional security technologies are ineffective in detecting or mitigating Advanced Persistent Threat. There are hundreds of variations in malware and their attack normally done in a same way. Moreover firewall, defense in depth, antivirus etc cannot protect the Advanced Persistent Threat [15], [22].

5. Network Security Threats Management

Computer and network surveillance is very much important and required in the information technology security system in recent days. Computer and network surveillance is need to maintain by the network manager to monitor the computer activity and database or stored data in a storage devices or hard disk. Moreover, Computer and network surveillance is responsible for the monitoring of data transformation of the network (within or outside of the network).

It is worthy to note that, in Computer and network surveillance monitoring is often carried out. And this may be performed by the government bodies, corporations and criminal organizations, or even individuals in many cases. Moreover this may be legal or illegal. In addition to this, Computer and network surveillance may required authentication or may not, based on requirement.

Apart from the Computer and Network Surveillance, a Network and System Administrators need to maintain following threat management principles and methods for secure, reliable, robust Information and Computer Network.

Computer Access Control is very much important and valuable for a healthy network administration. Computer Access Control includes the identification, authorization, authentication, access control over the computer systems and networks. In generally, Computer Access Control may also define as the techniques for allowing the computer system. Access is actually approved based on successful authentication and that may be based on following single/multiple facets.—

- Token including the Passwords
- Physical Keys
- Biometrics scan
- Electronic Keys
- Social barriers etc

Computer Access Control can be managed by capability based model or ACL based model. *Authorization* is the core job of Computer Access Control which allows following operations viz. Read, Write (including adding, updating, deleting, renaming etc), Execute. In Computer Access Control following are important viz.—

- Identification and Authorization
- Access Approval
- Accountability

Based on requirement, three most widely recognized models may be used for this methods viz. Discretionary Access Control (DAC), Mandatory Access Control (MAC), and Role Based Access Control (RBAC). However in special circumstances Network administrator can use following methods viz.—

- Attribute based Access Control
- Break Glass Access Control
- Access Control based on Responsibility
- Host based Access Control etc.

Hence, *Access control* is a kind of method of limiting access to a system or to physical or virtual resources and for secure and modern network management professionals need to manage all by proper strategies [2], [8], [17].

6. Application Security—

Application Security is very much important is Network Management and Administration and administrator should think about the security related affairs carefully. The Application Security

is responsible for the finding, fixing and preventing vulnerabilities in a system. There are different techniques in Application Security and among these few important are—

- Whitebox Security Review
- Blackbox Security Audit
- Design Review
- Tooling

All the computational programs may get the vulnerability and mobile devices in recent past may have various weakness. Some of the vulnerabilities are include—

- The application white listing
- Transport layer security consideration
- Strong and sophisticated authentication and authorization
- Sandboxing of applications and software.
- Processes associated with an user ID
- Interaction and relation of the mobile application and the OS
- Requiring user input for privileged access etc.

Application Security is requires different threats and attack and an Network Administrator need to solve all these routinely. And for proper application security following could be adopted—

- Antivirus and Malware
- Secure Coding
- Secure Operating Systems
- Secure Design etc.

Anti Virus and Anti Malware

It is worthy to note that different antivirus software and anti malware are very important for secure and robust security system establishment in a network or system; as modern antivirus is able to protect following—

- Malicious browser helper objects
- Browser hijackers
- Keyloggers and Backdoors
- Trojan horses and worms
- Spyware and adware etc.

Even few products are able in securing and threat management from the infected URLs, Spam, Online banking attacks etc. During the early days, antivirus become very rare in market but in late 2010's it is become important and mandatory in almost all types of organizations and

institutions and even individuals. Apart from the nontraditional files and documents, antivirus is become essential in general files protection as well such as in word file Macros can be inbuilt. In Security market, F-Secure was the first security organization that developed the Anti-Rootkit technology, called *BlackLight* and this was happens in the year 2005. In 2008, McAfee launched the McAfee Virus Scan in the market. In 2011, Protective Cloud Technology was developed by the AVG. There are different types of methods which antivirus engine may use to identify malware and among these following are important and valuable—

- Sandbox Detection
- Data Mining Techniques
- Signature based detection
- Heuristics systems
- Rootkit detection etc

However, in recent past organizations and institutions are providing importance in the Unified Threat Management, Hardware Firewall, Network Firewall, Cloud Antivirus, Online Scanning etc for protecting the system and networks [6], [19].

Secure Coding

Secure Coding is important for healthy and sophisticated information systems designing and development. Secure coding is a kind of technique in which special attention is provided on the designing and programming with security concern. The main reason for the vulnerabilities in software are include (but not limited to the following)—

- Insecure Defects
- Insecure Bugs
- Insecure logic flaws etc.

Today due to many insecure coding issues and incident, programmers and developers become aware of insecure coding causes and their remedies. For securing coding following methods may be adopted—

- Buffer Over-flow Protection
- Format String Attack Protection
- Integer Overflow Protection etc.

Hence it is worthy to apply defensive programming (Defensive programming is a technique which helps in improving software and source coding) for the development of secure software engineering.

Secure Design

Secure Designing is very important concept these days. Here software engineer need to think about the designing of securing software systems and programs from the foundation or initially. In recent past secure software development become core of attention and mainstream development. Domain driven designing is also very close with the secure designing concept. Fault tolerant program can be implemented for healthy and sophisticated programming. The two example of insecure designing are—

- Buffer Overflow
- Format String Vulnerabilities [5], [13].

In client server model, third party or hacker can be enter into the systems and based based on vulnerabilities can break the security.

Secure Operating System

Operating Systems security is the process for securing operating systems with different tools, techniques and mechanism. Operating Systems security is also responsible for the ensuring OS with better integrity, confidentiality, and availability. The OS Security is requires to built for the purposes like—

- Securing OS from the Threats and Virus
- Securing OS from the worms and malware
- Securing OS from the remote hacker intrusion

According to the TechnoPedia, the core aim of the Operating Systems security is include but not limited to the following—

- Performing a general and regular OS patch updates
- Installing as well as updating antivirus engines as well software
- For a securing Operating Systems, scrutinizing all incoming and outgoing network traffic through a firewall is very important and required.
- Creating secure accounts with proper user management is highly essential.

Throughout the world, companies are involved for the design and development of trusted operating systems and among these few important are listed (Wikipedia) in Table: 2

Table: 2- Few companies developed secure operating systems

Few Companies that developed Secure Operating Systems
Addamax (BSD, SVR3, SVR4, HP/UX) Argus Systems Group (Solaris, AIX, Linux) AT&T (System V) Bull (AIX) Digital Equipment Corporation (Ultrix) General Dynamics C4 Systems (Linux) Hewlett-Packard (HP/UX) Honeywell (Multics) IBM (OS/390, AIX) SCO (SCO Unix) SecureWare (Apple A/UX, HP/UX, SCO) Silicon Graphics (IRIX) Sun Microsystems (SunOS, Solaris) Trusted Information Systems (Xenix, Mach)

Network Administrators need to think and proper efforts for the development of Operating Systems with security.

Security by Default

This is another concept for the securing information systems designing and development. Security by default means keeping the systems and mechanism by default secure. Means keep the systems user friendly and by default secure. This approach may be developed and applied in the following—

- In operating systems
- In processor and Hardware
- In software development
- In Applications etc.

Secure by default thus very important and required concept these days for the development of overall secure information and network systems [7], [18].

Conclusion

Day by day, the concept of Security and Trust is very important. Initially security considered as Computer Security only, but these days this is increasing rapidly and thus the areas of Network security, web security, database security become important and valuable. There are different kind of attacks viz. Active attack and Passive attack and security measure is essential in all these areas. A Network Administrators these days need to hold the skills sets for other security areas as well. The skill set production is also very important and thus universities and training institutes

should establish different units and programs to produce human resources in the field. Cloud Computing Security and Mobile security is also very important for the secure systems these days.

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